

CONTEXTUALIZED AFRO-ASIAN LITERATURE MODULE AND STUDENTS' COMPREHENSION SKILLS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12074369>

ABSTRACT

Lambayong National High School, as the biggest high school in the Municipality of Lambayong looked on matters that would enhance their students' comprehension skills in order to respond to the call of equipping learners with the 21st century skills and become competent enough in facing the most complicated world outside the four corners of the classroom. This paper worked on the use of Contextualized Afro-Asian Literature Module and Students' Comprehension Skills. The study tested the acceptability of the contextualized materials in terms of its content, relevance, usability and instructional quality that was validated as highly acceptable. The researcher used experimental method of research to the 30 grade 8 students of Lambayong National High School and 30 for the control group, which were randomly selected. Findings revealed that students from the control group did not meet the expectations in their pre-test and post-test, while the experimental group's performance did not also meet the expectation in the pre-test but turned very satisfactory after the integration of contextualized Afro-Asian literature module. These results further explained with the use of t-test using 0.05 level of significance, which revealed that there is a significant difference between the mean gain score of control and experimental groups which mean that the experimental group improved the students' comprehension skills after the utilization of contextualized Afro-Asian Literature Module.

Keywords: *Contextualized, Afro-Asian, Literature, Comprehension Skills, Quantitative, Module*

INTRODUCTION

The entire nation offers a challenging environment for developing a language strategy that can benefit the entire country with its distinctive archipelagos and varied local languages in the area. As a result, during the past century, different language strategies have been introduced in the schools for each cohort. Nowadays, students are exposed to a variety of concepts, individuals, and goods; as a result, opinions develop as quickly as societal changes.

Internationally, studies on comprehension ability focus on the different factors that affect the low-comprehension skills of students in English specifically in teaching literature. In the study of Hasibuan, et.al 2019; and Wang et.al 2017 in China they made mentioned that contextualization can help enable the transformation and construction of a larger motivational environment for students but their study focus only on Mathematics. Even the study of Supiyati, et.al 2019, context is directly related to everyday life, where culture and environment assumed to motivate students to recognize mathematics as part of everyday life aim to enhance the student's ability, deepen their understanding of all forms of mathematics, and to make meaningful mathematical connections. However, these studies on contextualization of material in the field of English, they did not provide issues focusing on its impact in uplifting the student's comprehension skills in English.

In the Philippines, almost everyone is literate. This makes comprehension as an unending issue in language literacy. The pinnacle of reading proficiency and the cornerstone of all reading procedures is comprehension. According to some academics, it is the main goal of reading since "one who does not understand what one reads is deemed as if one has not read." It is really important to develop students' comprehension skills since this serves as the pillar of all learnings aspects (Allcott, 2021).

The Department of Education, along with the implementation of the K to 12, anchored all the learning competencies in teaching English to a specified literary piece and this becomes more challenging to the part of educators considering that students' nowadays find it so uninteresting in reading long passages from the textbooks.

Lambayong National High School, as the biggest high school in the Municipality of Lambayong looks on matters that would enhance their students' comprehension skills in order to respond to the call of equipping learners with the 21st century skills and become competent enough in facing the most complicated world outside the four corners of the classroom.

The researcher, as one of those language teachers who had encountered the same dilemma, never stops of discovering a certain approach that would somehow address to this concern, and come with the experimentation of contextualized Afro-Asian Literature module in teaching literary folktales and its benefits on the students' comprehension skills.

Research Questions

Generally, the study focused on Contextualized Instructional Module in Afro-Asian Literature and Students' Comprehension Skills.

Specifically, this determined the following:

1. What is the extent of acceptability of Contextualized Afro-Asian Literature Module in developing students' comprehension skills in terms of:
 - a. Content;
 - b. Relevance;
 - c. Usability; and
 - d. Instructional Quality?
2. What is the level of comprehension skills in Afro-Asian Literature of control group in the pre-test and post-test results?
3. What is the level of comprehension skills of experimental group in their pre-test and post-test results in Literary Folktales?
4. What is the mean gain score of both control and experimental group?
5. Is there a significant difference on the comprehension skills of control group and experimental group in their pre-test result?
6. Is there a significant difference on the comprehension skills of control group and experimental group in their post-test result?
7. Is there a significant difference on the mean gain score of the comprehension skills of both control group and experimental group ?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized the experimental method of research. The experimental approach entails changing one variable to see if it affects another variable. This approach uses controlled research techniques and random subject selection to test a hypothesis (Cherry, 2022). It tested the acceptability of Contextualized Afro-Asian Literature Module in terms of content; relevance; usability and instructional quality. This module was used in the experimental group to determine its impact on the students' comprehension skills in Afro-Asian Literature.

Participants of the Study

The participants of this study utilized 60 Grade 8 students of Lambayong National High School, Lambayong, Sultan Kudarat, who were enrolled for the school year 2019-2020. Respondents were chosen since their grade level primarily deals on Afro-Asian Literature in their English subject. A total of 30 grade 8 Emerald students was included in the control group and 30 grade 8 Amethyst students were utilized for the experimental group.

Sampling Technique

The selection of respondents was based on random sampling. The researcher randomly chose two sections from 10 Grade 8 classes in Lambayong National High School that represented the control and experimental groups. The researcher utilized draw lots method wherein she folded 10 paper slips and mark it with the letter C for the Control Group and another paper slip marked with letter E for the Experimental Group. The control group was taught using the traditional way. Traditional way of teaching signifies the use of board, paper and pen in the teaching process and included the whole passage from the book also. Further, the other group utilized Contextualized Afro-Asian Literature Module.

Data Gathering Instrument

The result of the study were gathered using survey questionnaire that assessed the acceptability of contextualized afro-asian literature module in terms of content, relevance, usability, and instructional quality. The survey questionnaire were rated by specialists in language teaching.

A researcher-modified tests anchored in the Learning Materials of Grade 8 issued by the Department of Education was used in the items that measured students' comprehension skills in Literary Folktales focusing on Afro-Asian Literature.

Data Gathering Procedure

The validation of the researcher's developed module was evaluated by Language Teaching experts to assure the acceptability of Contextualized Afro-Asian Literature Module.

After such, a letter was sent to the Schools Division Superintendent seeking permission for the researcher to administer the instrument on "Contextualized Afro-Asian Literature Module and The Students' Comprehension Skills.

Another letter was given to the school principal of Lambayong National High school asking permission to use the school as the venue of the study specifically, at the same time sought permit to utilize the Grade 8 students as participants for the study conducted.

The administration of the questionnaire was done personally by the researcher so that proper responses was elicited. The retrieval of the questionnaire was done right after the respondents answered the questionnaire. The data was then consolidated and interpreted.

Data Analysis

The frequency count, percentage, mean, and t-test were used to assess the data the researcher collected. The acceptability of Contextualized Afro-Asian Literature

Module in terms of content, relevance, usability, and instructional quality was described using frequency counts, percentages, and means.

Frequency count, mean and percentage was as well utilized in interpreting data that answered SOP 2, 3, and 4. The t-test was used to analyze the significant difference between the control group and experimental group on their comprehension skills in Afro-Asian Literary Folktales as well as their mean gain score that corresponded SOP 5, 6, and 7.

Scope and Limitations

The study was conducted at Lambayong National High School, focusing on enhancing the comprehension skills of Grade 8 students through the use of a contextualized Afro-Asian Literature module. The research scope included testing the acceptability of the module in terms of content, relevance, usability, and instructional quality, using an experimental method with a sample size of 60 students, divided equally into an experimental group and a control group. Despite the significant improvement observed in the experimental group, the study was limited by its relatively small sample size and the specific demographic and educational context of Lambayong National High School, which may affect the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, the study was constrained to a single grade level and did not account for long-term retention of comprehension skills or potential differences in individual student backgrounds and learning styles.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Table 1
Acceptability of Contextualized Afro-Asian Literature Module in the Students' Comprehension Skills

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
Content	4.10	Highly Acceptable
Relevance	4.15	Highly Acceptable
Usability	4.25	Very Highly Acceptable
Instructional Quality	4.25	Very Highly Acceptable
Over-all Mean	4.19	Highly Acceptable

Table 1 shows the acceptability of contextualized Afro-Asian Literature Module among Grade 8 students of Lambayong National High School. It portrays that the highest was garnered by usability and instructional quality with a section mean of 4.25 respectively and described as very highly acceptable. It was followed by relevance obtaining a section mean of relevance and content got the lowest mean of 4.10 in which all the indicators were described as highly acceptable. It further elaborated that an over-

all mean of 4.19 signifies that contextualized Afro-Asian Literature Module is highly acceptable, wherein 80-89 % of the contextualized material followed the set standards in making instructional material.

This was contradicted by the results in the study of İter (2017) which showed that the majority of teachers in their context, use lower-level strategies and practices when teaching contexts in their classrooms. In the context of their instruction for students to develop their learning skills, these teachers were not found to be using tactics that support the generally recognized knowledge and concepts about context teaching.

Table 2
Comprehension Skills of Control Group in their Pre-Test and Post-Test Results

Group	n	Pre Test			Post Test		
		Mean	TR	Description	Mean	TR	Description
Control	30	21.6	61	DNME	165.47	73	DNME

Legend:

DNME - Did Not Meet Expectations

TR – Transmuted Rating

Results above signifies the pretest and posttest scores of the control group of this study. It implies that the control group obtains the mean score of 21.6 with a transmuted rating of 61 which implies that the comprehension skills of the group in the pretest did not meet expectation. On the other hand, the group's posttest mean score still did not meet expectation gaining a mean score of 165.47 transmuted into 72. This further explains that the comprehension skills of the control group using the usual delivery of teaching in a classroom did not bid remarkable difference on their comprehension skills.

As a support to this result, McLaughlin (2002), mentioned that it is vital to split the concepts and explain tactics as more complex than various, individual talents or procedures in order to distinguish proficient readers. The justification is that employing certain skills is not as necessary as employing strategies, which necessitates the reader's usage of extra ways or tactics. Learners that encounter complex context can become more confused, which can result in less successful outcomes.

Table 3
Comprehension Skills of Experimental Group in their Pre-Test and Post-Test Results

Group	n	Pre Test			Post Test		
		Mean	TR	Description	Mean	TR	Description
Experimental	30	20.93	61	DNME	237.47	86	VS

Legend:

DNME - Did Not Meet Expectations
TR – Transmuted Rating
VS – Very Satisfactory

The table above presents the result on the comprehension skills of the experimental group. This portrays that the pretest mean score of the group is 20.93 transmuted into 61 which means that the result did not meet expectations. In addition, the group's posttest mean score is 237.47 with transmuted rating of 86 which was described as very satisfactory. This could be further interpreted that after the integration of contextualized Afro-Asian Literature Module among the grade 8 students, their comprehension skills increase further.

This was supported by Roe (2014) wherein he stated that reading and learning is highly intertwined, and consciousness in the learning process, knowledge about learning strategies, and abilities to use the strategies adequately are considered vital. Therefore, being able to separate students who have a strong chance of becoming high proficiency readers from those who are more likely to struggle with reading comprehension may be useful for teachers.

Table 4
Mean Gain Score of Control and Experimental Group

	Pre Test	Post Test	Mean Gain Score	TR	Description
Control	21.6	165.47	143.87	71	DNME
Experimental	20.93	237.47	216.54	82	S

Legend:

DNME - Did Not Meet Expectations
TR – Transmuted Rating
S – Satisfactory

Table 4 indicates the mean gain score among the participants of the study in both the control and experimental groups. It also elaborates that the mean gain score of the control group is 143.87 transmuted into 71 and its gain did not meet expectation. Furthermore, result implies that the mean gain score of the experimental group is 216.54 with a transmuted rating of 82 that symbolizes a satisfactory gain.

The above result is also congruent to the study of Ngag (2023), that the use of contextualized module manifested noticeable progress on students' learning in literature; therefore, it should be adopted by the schools, especially Indigenous Peoples (IPs) schools with IP members and be integrated into their classroom program.

Analysis on the Comprehension Skills of Control and Experimental Groups

One facet of linguistic proficiency that the learner must achieve is comprehension. Every topic calls for reading comprehension since reading is an integral part of every instruction. Students must thus possess strong comprehension skills.

Table 5
Results of T-Test Analysis on The Comparison of Pretest Scores Between Control Group and Experimental Group

Group	n	Mean	df	t-comp	t-tab	Interpretation
Control	30	21.6	58	0.22	2.001	Not Significant
Experimental	30	20.93				

α=0.05 level of significance

Results in this table elaborate the t-test analysis on the comparison of the pretest scores between the control and experimental groups. Data was tested using t-test at 0.05 level of significance and 58 degrees of freedom. It shows that the t-computed value is 0.22 and t-tabulated value is 2.001 Since the t-computed value is lesser than the t-tabulated data this could be interpreted as not significant and the first null hypothesis is accepted. These further states that the pretest scores of the two group is comparable. Therefore, this table implies that there is no significant difference between the pretest result of the control and experimental groups.

Table 6
Results of T-Test Analysis on the Comparison of Posttest Scores Between Control Group and Experimental Group

Group	n	Mean	df	t-comp	t-tab	Interpretation
Control	30	165.47	58	18.61	2.001	Significant
Experimental	30	237.47				

α=0.05 level of significance

Result portrays the comparison between the posttest result of control group and experimental group. Table presents data that were tested through t-test using 0.05 level of significance. It reveals that the t-computed value of 18.61 is greater than the t-tabulated value of 2.001, this only means that the second null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, result indicates that there is a significant difference between the posttest scores of both control group and experimental group.

The findings corroborated Brown's (2007) claim that there are still several issues with reading comprehension acquisition. Students are occasionally just needed to read the material aloud before responding to questions about its subject matter. It is a method that excludes pupils' ability to think, preventing them from engaging in an active reading process.

Table 7
Results of T-Test Analysis on the Comparison of Mean Gain Scores Between Control Group and Experimental Group

Group	n	Mean	df	t-comp	t-tab	Interpretation
Control	30	143.87	58	15.63	2.001	Significant
Experimental	30	216.53				

α=0.05 level of significance

Table 7 consists result on the comparison of the mean gain score between the two participating groups. This was analyzed through t-test with 0.05 level of significance. It shows that the t-computed value is 15.63 and the t-tabulated value is 2.001 at 58 degrees of freedom. This further reveal that since the t-computed value obtained a higher result than the t-tabulated data this signifies to reject the third null hypothesis. Finally, it can be said that after the integration of the contextualized afro-asian literature module in the literary folktales of Grade 8 that there is a significant difference between the mean gain scores of controls and experimental groups. Therefore, contextualized Afro-Asian Literature Module improves the comprehension skills of the students.

Conclusions

In the light of the findings derived from this study, the following conclusions were deemed:

1. The contextualized Afro-Asian Literature Module is highly acceptable in terms of content, relevance, usability and instructional quality in teaching literary folktales. Thus, the integration of contextualized Afro-Asian Literature Module improved the comprehension skills of the experimental group.
 2. Results further reveals that there is no significant difference between the pretest results of both groups, while their posttest results had a significant difference. Results further revealed that there is a significant difference between the mean gain score of control group and experimental group.
 3. Contextualized Module played a vital role in uplifting the comprehension skills of the students in Afro-Asian Literature, therefore, it is rewarding to say that the integration of Contextualized Instructional Module is highly acceptable in teaching Literary Folktales among Grade 8 students of Lambayong National High School and further improved the comprehension skills of the students.
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Recommendations

The following are the recommendations of the study based on the findings:

1. Language teachers may uplift the acceptability of contextualized Afro-Asian Literature Module through improving its content that provides opportunities for reflection and planning and include contents that are realistic and logical.
2. Department Head in English of Lambayong National High School may include in the conduct of LAC sessions the discussion in improving further the utilization of contextualized materials in language teaching to further elicit comprehension among students.
3. School administrators as well as language supervisors may consider the contextualized instruction in the teaching learning process for them to help in designing lessons that were contextualized to strengthen the comprehension skills of the students.
4. Using of Contextualized Afro-Asian Literature Module improved the students' comprehension skills. It is suggested for other researchers to use contextualized material as one the references in teaching reading.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study adhered to strict ethical standards to ensure the protection and well-being of all participants involved. Prior to the commencement of the study, approval was obtained from the relevant educational authorities at Lambayong National High School, ensuring that the research was conducted in accordance with institutional guidelines.

Informed consent was obtained from the parents or guardians of the Grade 8 students, clearly explaining the purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits of the study. Participation was entirely voluntary, and students were assured that their grades or standing in school would not be affected by their decision to participate or withdraw from the study at any time.

Confidentiality was rigorously maintained throughout the research process. All data collected were anonymized, and individual responses were kept confidential, accessible only to the researcher. The experimental and control groups were treated with equal respect and consideration, ensuring that no undue pressure or coercion was applied. Additionally, the study was designed to minimize any potential harm or discomfort to the students, with the content of the contextualized Afro-Asian Literature module being appropriate and sensitive to the cultural and developmental levels of the participants.

The findings of the study were reported honestly and accurately, with no fabrication, falsification, or inappropriate data manipulation. Any potential conflicts of interest were disclosed, and the study's limitations were acknowledged transparently. By adhering to these ethical principles, the study ensured the integrity of the research process and the welfare of the student participants.

Acknowledgments

In every journey, success is a collective effort, and the researcher wishes to acknowledge those who significantly aided in this study.

Special thanks go to Samson L. Molao, EdD, university president, and Mildred F. Accad, PhD, graduate school dean, for their support and guidance. Profound gratitude is extended to adviser Prof. Eva C. Polo, MAT, and committee members Cristobal C. Ambayon, PhD, Prof. Marjorie P. Lumogdang, Adrian Protacio, PhD, statistician Dr. Reynaldo Dalayap, Jr., and critic reader Amira Mae C. Gumanoy, PhD, for their expertise.

Thanks to validation experts Josephine L. Kabugatan, MT-II, Annabelle G. Baldonado, MT-II, and Instructor Jaime Boy Ngag Jr. Gratitude is also given to Dr. Raphael C. Fontanilla, CESO V, and Haron M. Kabugatan, for permitting the study, as well as the Grade 8 students of Lambayong National High School for their participation.

The researcher extends heartfelt thanks to friends Bai Laga S. Bantilan and Mojamel K. Pasandalan, her mother Pariha K. Sabal, her late father, her husband Datu Sherhan B. Mokalid, her children, and her siblings for their inspiration and support.

Above all, thanks to Allah (s.w.t) for the strength, wisdom, and confidence throughout this journey.

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